

Full Length Article

Meta-analysis and mapping of the monetary value of Mediterranean seagrass ecosystem services

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ABSTRACT

Seagrass meadows in the Mediterranean Sea deliver a broad range of services that benefit the economy and human welfare, yet they remain substantially undervalued in policy decisions. This study systematically reviewed 511 publications, with 17 qualifying for meta-analysis, providing 91 observations (predominantly in the northwestern Mediterranean) across eight ecosystem services (coastal protection, water purification, food provision, climate regulation, biotic materials and biofuels, life cycle maintenance, recreation and tourism, and cognitive effects). Employing a meta-regression model and standardizing values to International dollars (Int.\$) per hectare per year (with 2020 as the reference year), the economic value of these services was quantified. A key factor influencing the values of seagrass ecosystem services was the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita. The model projected the total annual value of Mediterranean seagrass ecosystem services at approximately 11.6 billion Int.\$/yr, with substantial country-specific variations. Italy had the highest valuation, while Slovenia the lowest. The average per hectare value of seagrass ecosystem services was estimated at 8,712 Int.\$/ha/yr. This research highlights the utility of meta-analysis and benefit transfer in shaping policy, especially where direct valuation studies are lacking, and emphasizes the need for further seagrass valuation research, particularly in underrepresented Mediterranean regions and less-studied ecosystem services.

1. Introduction

Seagrass meadows provide numerous essential services for human welfare (Barbier et al., 2011; Campagne et al., 2015), such as lifecycle support for exploited species (Cullen-Unsworth and Unsworth, 2013), coastal protection (Boudouresque et al., 2016), climate regulation (Pergent-Martini et al., 2021), recreational activities (Stamatiadou et al., 2023), water purification (Vance et al., 2022), and others. Seagrasses are highly sensitive to climate change (Chefaoui et al., 2018), invasive species (Katsanevakis et al., 2014) and several human activities (Micheli et al., 2013), necessitating urgent management and conservation measures (Griffiths et al., 2020). The concept of ecosystem services has become a critical framework for integrating social, economic, and ecological perspectives into research and environmental policy (Braat and de Groot, 2012). While previous studies have focused on qualitatively assessing the ecological functions and services provided by seagrass meadows (e.g., Salomidi et al., 2012), their economic valuation remains understudied.

An early effort by Costanza et al. (1997) estimated the global

monetary value of seagrass and algal beds at 30,538 Int.\$/ha/yr (all values have been converted to International dollars, using 2020 as the base year for comparison). A later review by Dewsbury et al. (2016) highlighted significant variability in valuations depending on the assessed ecosystem service types, region, and methodology. For example, the nursery ecosystem service in Indonesia was estimated at 97 Int.\$/ha/yr (Unsworth et al., 2010), while a range of ecosystem services in the Mediterranean Sea were collectively valued at 3.8 million Int.\$/ha/yr (Vassallo et al., 2013). Campagne et al. (2015) made a seminal contribution to the economic assessment of seagrasses in the Mediterranean, assigning monetary values to seven ecosystem services through benefit transfer, leveraging averages from prior studies. Valuations ranged from a low of 2 Int.\$/ha/yr for bioindicator services to a high of 306 Int.\$/ha/yr for carbon sequestration. However, these studies did not account for value fluctuations contingent on regional specificities. Additionally, spatial analyses of ecosystem service values remain limited, with most studies typically confined to small areas (Casas et al., 2021), which poses a significant challenge for policy formulation (Campagne et al., 2015; Dewsbury et al., 2016). This challenge is further

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complicated by the diversity of ecosystem service types, methodologies, and contextual factors, making it difficult to generate universally applicable monetary valuations.

Meta-regression is a powerful meta-analytic approach that uses statistical models to analyze and combine the findings from multiple primary studies (Stanley and Jarrell, 2005). Meta-regression models enable the derivation of benefit transfer functions with more general applicability and lower sensitivity to study-specific features. Benefit transfer is a valuable tool in the valuation of ecosystem services, permitting the unit value of a service or its benefit function to be transferred from existing studies (Navrud and Ready, 2007; Johnston and Rosenberger, 2010). Compared to using individual values, utilizing meta-analysis data for benefit transfer is advantageous in terms of minimizing carryover errors and generating reliable and precise ecosystem service valuations (Johnston and Rosenberger, 2010; Kaul et al., 2013). Meta-regression models have been utilized in the scientific literature to predict the values of ecosystem services associated with different habitats (Brander et al., 2012; Grammatikopoulou and Vačkářová, 2021), for individual ecosystem services (e.g., coastal protection) (Rao et al., 2015; Hynes et al., 2018), and for the spatial extent of the study area (e.g., national) (Zhou et al., 2020).

The seagrasses of the Mediterranean Sea are crucial for providing essential ecosystem services, supporting environmental quality, and contributing to regional economic growth (Short et al., 2007). Mediterranean seagrasses, i.e. *Posidonia oceanica*, *Cymodocea nodosa*, *Zostera marina*, and *Nanozostera noltei*, contribute diverse ecosystem services that vary across species (Mtwana Nordlund et al., 2016). However, seagrasses are vulnerable to natural and anthropogenic stressors, particularly coastal development, towed fishing gear, and anchoring (Boudouresque et al., 2009; Giakoumi et al., 2015; Montefalcone et al., 2019). The absence of unified practices for spatial planning and marine management across the countries of this semi-closed basin exacerbates these challenges (Mazor et al., 2013; Katsanevakis et al., 2015). The comprehensive valuation and mapping of seagrass services, along with their interactions with human activities and the socio-economic attributes of coastal regions, remain insufficient, hindering seagrass conservation and restoration in the Mediterranean.

To address the identified gaps, the principal objective and scientific question of this study is to ascertain the economic value of the ecosystem services provided by seagrass meadows. This was achieved by developing a framework that systematically quantifies and maps the monetary value of these services in the Mediterranean. Using information from the literature and incorporating environmental and socio-economic factors to create a meta-function, the framework generates a comprehensive valuation map, serving as a vital tool for policymakers and stakeholders to support more informed and cohesive conservation strategies.

2. Methodology

The methodology for assessing the benefits and monetary values of Mediterranean seagrass meadows involved a value transfer approach based on a meta-regression model. This process allowed for spatial valuation based on various predictors. The research consisted of three distinct phases:

I. Database development

a. **Systematic Review.** A comprehensive database of economic valuations of ecosystem services provided by seagrass meadows in the Mediterranean Sea was created.

b. **Data Acquisition and Normalization.** Data from various studies were standardized, converting monetary values to a common spatial, temporal, and currency format (Int.\$/ha/yr – 2020 as a reference year for monetary values).

II. **Meta-analysis.** Statistical models were employed, when possible, to investigate the key factors driving the variability in

ecosystem service values. This step also involved defining the explanatory variables for meta-regression. For ecosystem services with a scarcity of data, simple averages of available values were estimated.

III. **Benefit Transfer Application.** Values were attributed to each seagrass meadow based on site-specific characteristics, and these values were subsequently mapped to illustrate spatial variations.

2.1. Database creation

The employed systematic review aimed to classify, systematize, and analyze the characteristics, trends, and monetary values of Mediterranean seagrass ecosystems. The review adhered to the PRISMA 2020 (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) protocol and the practical guide by Foo et al. (2021) on the implementation of systematic and meta-analysis reviews.

The central research question of the systematic review was: “What is the monetary value of seagrass meadow ecosystem services in the Mediterranean Sea?”. We employed an adapted PECO framework (Population, Exposure, Comparator, Outcome), which is traditionally used in medical science and has been increasingly adopted in environmental sciences to guide systematic reviews (Foo et al., 2021) (Table 1).

Search strings (Table 1) were applied to Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar on 11 September 2024 (Fig. 1). Additionally, data were retrieved from ESVD (Ecosystem Services Valuation Database) and TEEB (The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity), yielding 511 unique papers.

Initial screening was conducted based on the Title, Abstract, and keywords of the retrieved papers. The inclusion criteria were: (i) Is the study about seagrasses? (ii) Is the study about ecosystem services? (iii) Is a monetary valuation conducted? and (iv) Is the study area in the Mediterranean Sea? As a result of the first screening, 422 papers were excluded as they failed to meet one or multiple criteria (Fig. 1).

The 89 studies that passed the initial screening were enriched with 19 additional papers through snowballing (i.e., the practice of utilizing the citations within a paper to discover more related papers; Wohlin, 2014). All 108 papers underwent full-text screening based on the same criteria (Fig. 1). Additionally, papers were reviewed for information required for calculating monetary values in International \$/ha/yr (Int. \$/ha/yr). This rigorous process resulted in additional exclusions based on the set criteria or redundancy. Specifically, 89 studies were excluded for not meeting one or more of the inclusion criteria, and two studies were excluded because they merely replicated information from prior studies already in the database, without contributing original case studies or novel information (Fig. 1).

A database, formed from 17 selected papers, was established to integrate the existing knowledge on the economic valuation of the

Table 1
PECO factors and the terms used as strings to research engines.

Population of Interest:	<i>“seagrass*” OR “Posidonia oceanica” OR “Cymodocea nodosa” OR “Zostera marina” OR “Zostera noltei” AND “Mediterranean” OR “Albania” OR “Bosnia” OR “Gibraltar” OR “Algeria” OR “Morocco” OR “France” OR “Croatia” OR “Montenegro” OR “Cyprus” OR “Libya” OR “Lebanon” OR “Egypt” OR “Malta” OR “Monaco” OR “Slovenia” OR “Syria” OR “Tunisia” OR “Turkey” OR “Greece” OR “Spain” OR “Israel” OR “Italy”</i>
Exposure:	<i>“ecosystem service*” OR “good*” OR “benefit*” OR “carbon sequestration” OR “blue carbon” OR “blue forest*” OR “food* provision*” OR “recreation*” OR “life cycle maintenance” OR “cultural*” OR “regulation*” OR “erosion*” OR “fishery” OR “wastewater*” OR “indicator*”</i>
Comparator:	NA, there is no comparator or control group
Outcome	<i>“monetary” OR “economic” OR “financial” OR “accounting” OR “capital” OR “willingness” OR “valuation*” OR “Euro*” OR “USD*”</i>

Fig. 1. Flow chart of literature review.

Mediterranean seagrass habitats. This database facilitated the standardization of seagrass ecosystem service values to Int.\$/ha/yr (with 2020 as a reference year) and enabled a meta-analysis to investigate the relationship between these values and site-specific features. The analysis of the papers focused on (a) publication details and the methodology used (according to the TEEB classification, (Pascual et al., 2011)), (b) specifics of each study, such as the type of ecosystem service assessed (following the classification by Liquete et al. 2013), and (c) information on the beneficiaries, i.e. individuals connected to the estimated value (for instance if we have an estimation of the willingness to pay from

fishers, we also need information about their population). Furthermore, each record in the database was enriched with data from external sources on the extent of the seagrass meadows in the study area of each published paper (EMODnet, 2024; Sini et al., 2017; Traganos et al., 2022; Duman et al., 2019; DFS Montenegro Engineering (2012); UNEP-WCMC, 2021), the coverage of Marine Protected Area (MPA) within the study area of each paper (EMODnet, 2024), population density of the adjacent coastal region (CIESIN, 2024; Lehner and Grill, 2013), and socio-economic indicators, such as the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita (World Bank, 2024). This selection of variables was informed

by a comprehensive review of literature and previous meta-analyses (Orth et al., 2006; de Groot et al., 2012; Quintas-Soriano et al., 2016; Chefaoui et al., 2018; de los Santos et al., 2019; Taye et al., 2021), aiming to elucidate factors influencing seagrass valuation, e.g. by affecting seagrass condition and its capacity to provide ecosystem services.

The literature review revealed diverse methodologies, metrics, currencies, and temporal scales, employed in studies of seagrass ecosystem services in the Mediterranean. To facilitate comparisons across these studies, all estimated values were converted into International dollars (Int.\$) per hectare as of 2020, in line with Van der Ploeg et al. (2010). The Int.\$ serves as a hypothetical unit of value, standardizing values across nations by adjusting to the same Purchasing Power Parity (PPP), equating one Int.\$ to one US dollar. Indicators required for normalization were sourced from the World Bank's open database. Moreover, in cases like willingness to pay assessments, additional data such as population size were needed to translate the estimated value into Int.\$/ha/yr. Studies lacking this requisite information were excluded based on the established selection criteria (Fig. 1).

2.2. Meta-analysis model and benefit transfer

Meta-regression analyses were conducted to synthesize estimates and assess variability from multiple primary studies (Nelson and Kennedy, 2009). Data were collected for eight types of ecosystem services, but only four (water purification, food provision, coastal protection, climate regulation) had sufficient data (>10 records) to be included in the regression model. For the other four (recreation and tourism, life cycle maintenance, cognitive effects, biotic material and biofuels), the average of available values for each ES was employed as the input for the benefit transfer process. The explanatory variables used in the model were GDP, population density, MPA coverage in the study area, seagrass coverage in the study area, and ES classification (water purification, food provision, coastal protection, climate regulation).

The meta-analytic regression formula is:

$$y_i = \alpha + b_S X_{Si} + b_M X_{Mi} + b_G X_{Gi} + b_{Sg} X_{Sgi} + b_P X_{Pi} + u_i \quad (1)$$

The dependent variable y_i represents the economic value of ecosystem service per hectare per year (Int.\$/ha/yr) for each record i . The term u_i denotes the error component, α is the constant, X_{Si} indicates the ES classification, X_{Mi} indicates the existence of MPA and X_{Gi} refers to the GDP, X_{Sgi} to the extent of seagrass meadows in the study area, and X_{Pi} refers to the population density, each with their respective coefficients.

In the existing literature, a variety of models have been proposed in meta-analyses to address issues of normality, homoscedasticity and multilinearity. The three most prevalent models have been examined in this study: (a) Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) (Hynes et al., 2018; Grammatikopoulou and Vačkářová, 2021; Kang et al., 2022), (b) Weighted Least Squares (WLS) (Chaikumbung et al., 2016), and (c) Panel Data (Fixed Effects (FE) or Random Effects (RE)) models (De Salvo and Signorello, 2015; Grammatikopoulou and Vačkářová, 2021). In the panel models, the "reference-id" of each study was used as a stratification variable to address the issue of multiple records from the same study. However, the Hausman test indicated that a FE model is more appropriate than an RE model, and the Lagrange Multiplier Test indicated that the OLS model provided a significantly better fit compared to the FE model, hence panel models were excluded from further analysis. For both the WLS and OLS, all combinations of the candidate predictor variables were considered, and model selection was based on the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC).

A natural logarithm transformation was applied to both the continuous explanatory variables and the dependent variable to meet modeling assumptions and improve model fit. In the OLS model, as recommended in the literature (Hynes et al., 2018; Grammatikopoulou and Vačkářová, 2021), White's standard errors were employed to

address heteroskedasticity; no multicollinearity was detected (the maximum Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was 1.2). In the WLS model, although inverse variance is typically recommended as the weight, the unavailability of standard errors in this dataset necessitated using the inverse square root of the sample size as an alternative (Chaikumbung et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2022), no heteroscedasticity and multicollinearity were detected (maximum VIF of 1.3; Breusch-Pagan test showed no evidence of heteroscedasticity). Eight outliers, identified through Box-Cox plots, were excluded.

To perform the benefit transfer, the collected data and the best meta-regression model (based on AIC) were utilized to estimate the per-hectare value of ecosystem services in the Mediterranean Sea and to generate their spatial distribution (mapping unit: Int.\$/ha/yr). Model-derived estimates were utilized for four ecosystem services and mean values for the remaining four. The total value of ecosystem services provided by seagrasses at each location was calculated by summing these eight values.

Seagrass distribution was mapped using multiple data sources: the EMODNET layer for the EU Mediterranean countries (excluding the Aegean Sea), the MARISCA layer for the Greek part of the Aegean Sea (Sini et al., 2017), data from Traganos et al. (2022) for Morocco, Egypt, Lebanon, Bosnia, Turkey, Libya, data from Duman et al. (2019) for Turkey, data from DFS Montenegro Engineering (2012) for Montenegro, and the Global Distribution of Seagrasses dataset for Croatia UNEP-WCMC (2021). Data on the distribution of seagrasses in the Mediterranean region were converted into vectors, merged into a pan-Mediterranean distribution map, and a grid with a resolution of approximately 1 ha was created. The values assigned to each cell for the four ecosystem services included in the meta-regression model were determined based on the specific values of the explanatory variables at each cell, while the average values for the remaining four services were derived from the database. At the country level, the total value of each ecosystem service was estimated by summing the values of all cells located within its Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ).

To evaluate the performance of the benefit transfer model, transfer errors were estimated (Zhou et al., 2020; Grammatikopoulou and Vačkářová, 2021), as:

$$TransferError = \frac{V_{tr} - V_{ob}}{V_{ob}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where the term V_{tr} is the mean transfer value and the term V_{ob} is the mean observed value (Kirchhoff et al., 1997). According to Navrud and Ready (2007) and Boyle and Parmeter (2017), transfer errors can be classified into four main scales: errors with absolute values < 20% indicate a good fit between modelled and observed values; errors between 20%–50% suggest an adequate fit; errors between 50%–100% are indicative of a poor fit; and errors > 100% indicate a very poor fit, suggesting that predictions based on the model results should be treated with caution.

The statistical analysis was performed using the R software, and the geospatial analysis was conducted using QGIS 3.22.

3. Results

3.1. Overview of economic valuation studies

Among the analyzed studies, 76% utilized estimations from earlier studies or data collected from previous research, while the remaining 24% used primary data. The studies were published between 2010 and 2024 (65% from 2020 and beyond) (See Supplementary file). In terms of geographic scale, 65% of the surveys were local, 23% national, and 12% regional. There was a pronounced research focus on the western Mediterranean, particularly Italy, in contrast to the relatively understudied eastern region (Fig. 2). Research effort predominantly concentrated on regulating ecosystem services, followed by provisioning and cultural.

Fig. 2. General descriptive analysis of 91 observations of monetary value of seagrass meadows ecosystem services. The distribution of investigated ecosystem service types is depicted in pie charts, with green representing regulating, orange provisioning, and pink cultural services. The alluvial diagrams illustrate the categorized types of ecosystem services and their corresponding valuation methods. Additionally, the diagrams depict the scale of each study, the type of data used (either generated or also produced from the literature), and the number of ecosystem services valued. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Approximately 65% of the studies evaluated a single ecosystem service, 11% explored two, 17% studied four, and 7% estimated five ecosystem services. Climate regulation emerged as the most frequently studied service (34 records), often assessed using the avoided cost method. Water purification (16 records) was also extensively documented, mostly using the replacement cost method. Coastal protection (13 records) and food provision (12 records) commonly employed avoided cost and direct market pricing methods, respectively. For cultural ecosystem services, recreation and tourism was mostly studied (10 datasets), mainly through direct market pricing. The highest estimated

mean unit value was estimated for coastal protection at 10,894.6 Int. \$/ha/yr, while the lowest value was for cognitive effects at 3.6 Int. \$/ha/yr (Fig. 3). Notably, coastal protection, water purification, and climate regulation exhibited a wide range of values and diverse valuation methodologies. Conversely, provisioning services, primarily assessed via direct market pricing, showed more consistent estimates. Limited data were available for life cycle maintenance, cognitive effects, and biotic material and biofuels.

Fig. 3. The boxplots graphically represent the monetary valuations of ecosystem services by type, offering insights into their variations and similarities. To enhance the accuracy of the mean value and standard deviation estimations outliers (8 records) have been excluded from consideration. The outliers are represented by crosses in the figure. The different colors in the plot represent the method each study has employed. The values are estimated in terms of Int. \$/ha/yr, with 2020 as the reference year. The first line of the box represents the 1st quartile, the second represents the median, and the third represents the 3rd quartile. The whiskers extend from the top and bottom of the box to indicate the range of the data. Values in brackets next to the ecosystem service type represent the number of conducted studies.

3.2. Meta-regression model and monetary valuation of seagrasses

The model with the lowest AIC was the one with ecosystem service type and GDP per capita as predictor variables, based on OLS (Tables 2, S2). The positive coefficient for GDP per capita indicates that increases in GDP are associated with a higher valuation of ecosystem services. The coefficients of the four categories of ecosystem services indicate that climate change has the lowest and coastal protection the highest value (Table 2).

The meta-regression model was developed by incorporating only statistically significant variables to derive a meta-function. A wide range of monetary values for seagrass ecosystem services among countries in the region was revealed, ranging from 1,588 Int.\$/ha/yr in Morocco to 95,767 Int.\$/ha/yr in Monaco (Fig. 4). The significant variation among countries is attributed to the substantial disparity in their GDP per capita, with Monaco having a GDP of 182,538 \$ per capita, in stark contrast to Morocco's significantly lower figure of 3,258 \$ per capita.

The estimated annual value of seagrass ecosystem services in the Mediterranean was estimated at 11.6 billion Int\$/yr, with notable differences among countries (Fig. 4). The average per hectare value of seagrass ecosystem services in the Mediterranean Sea was estimated at 8,711 Int.\$/ha/yr. In Italy, with 381,810 ha of seagrass meadows, the average value was 14,862 Int.\$/ha/yr, resulting in a total national value of 5.6 billion Int.\$/yr; the highest among Mediterranean countries and approximately 48% of the region's annual value (Fig. 4 and Table 3). In contrast, Slovenia, harboring only 6 ha of seagrass meadows and a lower value of 11,763 Int.\$/ha/yr due to its lower GDP registered a total value of 70,575 Int.\$/yr, ranking last among Mediterranean countries (Fig. 4 and Table 3). Despite Tunisia's relatively low mean value of 1,686 Int.\$/ha/yr, its extensive seagrass coverage of 401,942 ha propelled its total valuation to 677 million Int.\$/yr, placing it fifth in overall national value (Fig. 4 and Table 3). Monaco, despite its limited 102 ha of seagrasses, achieved a valuation of 9.7 million Int.\$/yr (Fig. 4 and Table 3).

The estimation of transfer errors varied significantly across ecosystem services and countries (Table S3). For food provision, the model demonstrated good fit in Italy and adequate fit in Tunisia. For climate regulation, the transfer error showed adequate fit in France, while results for other countries indicated a poor or very poor fit. In terms of coastal protection, Italy exhibited an adequate fit, but other countries showed very poor fits. For water purification, the transfer errors were either poor or very poor.

4. Discussion

The literature review identified a modest corpus of seventeen research articles dedicated to evaluating the ecosystem services

Table 2
Meta-regression results of the best Ordinary Least Square Model (OLS) with Huber-White robust standard errors based on AIC. Signif. codes: 0.001 '***' 0.01 '**' 0.05 '*' 0.1 '.'.

	Coefficient	St. Error	p-value	
Intercept (=Climate Regulation)	-5.92	3.56	1.01E-02	.
Coastal Protection	3.40	0.57	1.27E-07	***
Food	3.20	0.47	5.79E-09	***
Water Purification	2.91	0.61	1.32E-05	***
Gross Domestic Product (log)	1.08	0.37	5.13E-03	***
N	67			
R-squared	0.46			
Adjusted R-squared	0.43			
AIC	278.12			

provided by seagrass meadows in the Mediterranean Sea. This finding mirrors the dynamic evolution of research and valuation methodologies in this domain (Gómez-Baggethun et al., 2010). However, the tendency to undervalue and overlook the multiple benefits of coastal and marine ecosystems accentuates the critical importance of comprehensively assessing ecosystem services and their monetary value in marine settings (Barbier, 2017). Among the eight services assessed, three were represented by a scant number of records (≤ 2). Despite the widespread recognition of seagrasses as vital ecosystems offering a plethora of services (de los Santos et al., 2020), scholarly efforts tend to concentrate on certain services, such as food provision, employing a limited set of methodologies. Future studies should address underrepresented services, particularly those with few available records, and explore additional seagrass services, such as those provided by seagrass banquettes (Boudouresque et al., 2016). Furthermore, innovative methodologies should be developed to improve the valuation of seagrass meadows. Marine macroalgae, which often provide similar ecosystem services to seagrass meadows, are commonly studied separately. Future research could explore commonalities with seagrasses, thereby enriching the existing database with additional data.

Valuation studies were confined to only eight (of the 22) Mediterranean countries, with a strong focus on the northwestern Mediterranean, highlighting the need for localized or national assessments to capture the distinct attributes of each case study. This is particularly important when comparing or transferring values across diverse socio-economic contexts, as the level of resource dependency for critical services can vary significantly. For instance, while previous studies have spotlighted the critical role of fisheries in the Algerian economy (Maouel, Maynou and Bedrani, 2014), there was no dedicated study probing the monetary values of food provision services linked to seagrasses. In such cases, meta-regression modeling becomes valuable, offering preliminary but vital metric for policy formulation. It is recommended for future research, to explore alternative models and, as data availability improves, integrate a broader spectrum of explanatory variables to refine the analysis.

The meta-model was employed to evaluate ecosystem services by leveraging available data and predicting values in relation to the environmental and socio-economic characteristics of each location. However, the scarcity of studies meeting the inclusion criteria constrained the utilization of a broad array of explanatory variables. Obtaining spatial data for seagrass habitats was challenging compared to terrestrial habitats due to the inherent complexities of marine ecosystems (Maes et al., 2016). In addition, an even greater lack of data on the spatial ecological features of seagrass beds, such as root density and gaps caused by anchorage damage, further compromises the accuracy of valuation and mapping. Some of the considered explanatory variables exhibited negligible variations and failed to reach statistical significance, likely due to the paucity of available data (see Supplementary file). For example, although population density (as a surrogate of the intensity of human activities) is known to influence the status of seagrass meadows (Waycott et al., 2009), the minimal differences among the reviewed case studies was likely a reason to render it non-significant in the model.

Despite these limitations, the model explained an important part of total variance, aligning with similar studies in the field (Rao et al., 2015; Quintas-Soriano et al., 2016; Grammatikopoulou and Vačkářová, 2021). While comparable studies using a meta-regression model on seagrass ecosystem service values are lacking, a similar study on forests identified similar influential variables (GDP and type of ecosystem service) (Grammatikopoulou and Vačkářová, 2021). It is envisaged that the future augmentation of the dataset with new studies will enhance the model's predictive capacity, yielding deeper insights into the factors affecting the value of seagrass services.

Geographic variation in benefit transfer is evident (Fig. 4), with the African coastline typically exhibiting low values, a reflection of their lower GDP and rudimentary seagrass mapping. Conversely, the northwestern Mediterranean exhibits elevated unit values and comprehensive

Table 3
The total values per ecosystem service per country, along with their aggregate values, are displayed. The mean value represents the sum of all eight ecosystem services per map cell (≈ 1 ha) per year. The sum of the map cells indicates the area of seagrass meadows per country. The symbol (D) indicates that the ecosystem service value has been transferred using the mean value from the database, excluding outliers. The symbol (OLS) indicates that the ecosystem service value has been transferred using the meta-function, based on the results of the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model with White's standard errors.

Country	Recreation and tourism (D)	Life cycle maintenance (D)	Cognitive effects (D)	Biotic material and biofuels (D)	Water purification (OLS)	Coastal protection (OLS)	Food provision (OLS)	Climate regulation (OLS)	Total value (8 ES)	Mean value (all ES)	Map cells (Seagrass area)
	<i>(Int.\$/Country/yr)</i>										
Albania	33,641	185,777	15,063	1,541,447	2,621,919	4,279,801	3,504,005	142,831	12,324,483	2,455	5,021
Algeria	25,212	139,231	11,289	1,155,241	1,184,589	1,933,624	1,583,117	64,531	6,096,834	1,620	3,763
Bosnia	3,665	20,239	1,641	167,929	325,167	530,775	434,562	17,714	1,501,691	2,745	547
Croatia	173,677	959,114	77,766	7,958,054	38,982,729	63,632,141	52,097,590	2,123,613	166,004,684	6,404	25,922
Cyprus	78,846	435,416	35,304	3,612,776	36,898,846	60,230,585	49,312,632	2,010,092	152,614,496	12,969	11,768
Egypt	1,474	8,140	660	67,540	70,636	115,301	94,400	3,848	361,999	1,645	220
France	599,724	3,311,907	268,533	27,479,877	401,480,221	655,342,677	536,549,203	21,870,928	1,646,903,070	18,399	89,511
Greece	1,041,535	5,751,761	466,359	47,724,071	295,865,812	482,946,564	395,403,204	16,117,506	1,245,316,812	8,011	155,453
Italy	2,558,127	14,126,970	1,145,430	117,215,670	1,376,819,928	2,247,405,500	1,840,019,998	75,003,270	5,674,294,894	14,862	381,810
Lebanon	14,083	77,774	6,306	645,314	1,157,298	1,889,076	1,546,645	63,045	5,399,541	2,569	2,102
Libya	321,185	1,773,706	143,814	14,716,966	36,538,923	59,643,076	48,831,620	1,990,484	163,959,774	3,420	47,938
Malta	37,614	207,718	16,842	1,723,498	18,242,014	29,776,735	24,379,128	993,747	75,377,296	13,427	5,614
Monaco	683.4	3,774	306	31,314	2,419,006	3,948,582	3,232,826	131,777	9,768,268	95,767	102
Montenegro	6,432	35,520	2,880	294,720	743,123	1,213,012	993,130	40,482	3,329,300	3,468	960
Morocco	77,251	426,610	34,590	3,539,710	3,536,774	5,773,134	4,726,643	192,668	18,307,381	1,588	11,530
Slovenia	40.2	222	18	1,842	17,015	27,773	27,739	926,878,2769	70,575	11,763	6
Spain	817,514	4,514,629	366,051	37,459,219	366,746,404	598,646,104	490,129,975	19,978,778	1,518,658,674	12,446	122,017
Tunisia	2,693,011	14,871,854	1,205,826	123,396,194	133,112,737	217,282,079	177,895,520	7,251,413	677,708,635	1,686	401,942
Turkey	480,437	2,653,159	215,121	22,014,049	62,440,368	101,922,426	83,447,024	3,401,485	276,574,069	3,857	71,707

Quantifying ecosystem services in monetary terms equips scientists and policymakers with a unified metric, facilitating the development of strategies that harmonize ecological sustainability with socio-economic objectives (Tammi et al. 2017). The adoption of monetary units in this context does not constitute a form of commodification of nature; rather, it serves as a strategy to underscore the substantial contribution of ecosystems to human welfare. The articulation of value in monetary terms enables spatial comparisons and informed governance of human activities, employing zoning systems to prioritize conservation and regulate impacting activities. For instance, incorporating ecosystem service value maps into cost-benefit analyses (Brander et al., 2020) can support a holistic approach that supports decision-making regarding the expansion of Mediterranean MPAs. Furthermore, understanding the economic value of ecosystem services enhances policymakers' capacity to recognize and address the environmental costs of economic activities, supporting policies that mitigate harmful impacts and promote the protection and restoration of natural capital for future generations (Petersen et al., 2018). By accounting for both tangible and intangible benefits, often overlooked by traditional economic metrics, this methodology provides a comprehensive and nuanced framework, empowering policymakers to make decisions that balance immediate economic priorities with long-term ecological resilience and human well-being.

Seagrass meadows are increasingly imperiled by an array of challenges, including the climate crisis, invasive species, heterogeneous management policies, and escalating anthropogenic pressures (Unsworth et al., 2019). Over the coming decades, the total value of seagrass meadows will be impacted as their unitary value shifts in response to different socio-economic scenarios (Kubiszewski et al., 2017). Additionally, the area covered by seagrass meadows is projected to decline significantly due to climate change, with a potential loss of up to 75% of *Posidonia oceanica* (the dominant species in the Mediterranean Sea) by 2050 (Chefaoui et al., 2018). This would dramatically alter the state of these ecosystems and disrupt the critical ecosystem services they provide.

The economic significance of seagrass ecosystem services, as illuminated by our findings, highlights the imperative for policymakers to integrate these services into their decision-making processes. The protection of seagrass habitats necessitates a holistic assessment across the Mediterranean and the enactment of cohesive policies, recognizing that local interventions can wield profound influences on socio-ecological systems at regional and even global scales (Bennett et al., 2015; Katsanevakis et al., 2015). The essential decline of seagrass beds in Gulf of Gabes, Africa, serves as a prime example of suboptimal habitat management in the Mediterranean. Largely unregulated human activities, particularly phosphate fertilizer pollution, have resulted in a drastic 90% decline in seagrass coverage in this region (El Zrelli et al., 2023). This loss does not only bears local repercussions but also exerts substantial impacts on climate regulation beyond national borders. Future research efforts must pivot towards a more rigorous assessment of the ecosystem services along Africa's coastlines, prioritizing the acquisition of primary data over the reliance on benefit transfer from disparate regions and countries (Kenter et al., 2011). Conducting case studies that assimilate the viewpoints and experiences of local stakeholders is paramount, as this approach can yield insights of enhanced authenticity and relevance.

Acknowledging the inherent limitations and uncertainties in our analysis, this study nonetheless offers the most updated and comprehensive assessment to date of the monetary value of seagrass ecosystem services across the Mediterranean. Our work enriches the ongoing methodological discourse by underscoring the pertinence of employing value transfer estimates, thereby fostering their refinement and enhancing their reliability. Additionally, the econometric estimates utilized in this study elucidate key determinants that modulate the valuation of seagrass services in diverse spatial contexts. Consequently, our findings serve as a valuable resource for policymakers, providing them with empirical grounding to prioritize seagrass conservation and

refine marine spatial planning initiatives.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights the urgent need for a more comprehensive understanding and valuation of seagrass ecosystem services in the Mediterranean Sea. Despite encountering challenges like limited data and methodological constraints, our findings highlight the economic importance of seagrass meadows and stress the necessity of incorporating these values into policy decisions. We emphasize the vital role of a comprehensive regional conservation strategy and effective measures, such as well-connected networks of MPAs in protecting seagrass habitats and their services. Moving forward, it is crucial to address imminent threats to seagrass ecosystems, such as pollution and habitat degradation, through collaborative efforts involving local stakeholders. Priority should be given to collecting data from understudied regions, such as the African coastlines. By bridging gaps in knowledge and methodology, our study contributes to advancing the discourse on ecosystem service valuation. It also equips policymakers with actionable insights to guide conservation strategies and marine spatial planning initiatives for the sustainable management of seagrass ecosystems.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the author(s) used ChatGPT to improve the grammar and syntax of the text as non-native speakers. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as necessary and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Valentini Stamatiadou: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Antonios D. Mazaris:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Stelios Katsanevakis:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2025.101704>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Barbier, E.B., et al., 2011. The value of estuarine and coastal ecosystem services. *Ecol. Monogr.* 81 (2), 169–193. <https://doi.org/10.1890/10-1510.1>.
- Barbier, E.B., 2017. Marine ecosystem services. *Curr. Biol.* 27 (11), R507–R510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2017.03.020>.
- Bennett, E.M., et al., 2015. Linking biodiversity, ecosystem services, and human well-being: three challenges for designing research for sustainability. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 14, 76–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2015.03.007>.
- Boudouresque, C.F., et al., 2009. 'Regression of Mediterranean seagrasses caused by natural processes and anthropogenic disturbances and stress: a critical review', 52 (5), pp. 395–418. <https://doi.org/10.1515/BOT.2009.057>.
- Boudouresque, C.F., et al., 2016. The necromass of the *Posidonia oceanica* seagrass meadow: fate, role, ecosystem services and vulnerability. *Hydrobiologia* 781 (1), 25–42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10750-015-2333-y>.
- Boyle, K.J., Parmeter, C.F., 2017. 'Benefit Transfer for Ecosystem Services', in Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Environmental Science. <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780199389414.013.455>.
- Braat, L.C., de Groot, R., 2012. The ecosystem services agenda: bridging the worlds of natural science and economics, conservation and development, and public and private policy. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 1 (1), 4–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2012.07.011>.
- Brander, L.M., et al., 2020. The global costs and benefits of expanding Marine Protected Areas. *Mar. Policy* 116, 103953. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.103953>.
- Campagne, C.S., et al., 2015. The seagrass *Posidonia oceanica*: ecosystem services identification and economic evaluation of goods and benefits. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 97 (1), 391–400. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2015.05.061>.
- Casas, E., et al., 2021. 'Economic mapping and assessment of *Cymodocea nodosa* meadows as nursery grounds for commercially important fish species. A case study in the Canary Islands.', *One Ecosystem* [Preprint], (2). <https://go.gale.com/ps/i.do?p=AONE&sw=w&issn=&v=2.1&it=r&id=GALE%7CA674171168&sid=googleScholar&linkaccess=abs> (Accessed: 3 April 2023).
- Chaikumbung, M., Doucouliagos, H., Scarborough, H., 2016. The economic value of wetlands in developing countries: a meta-regression analysis. *Ecol. Econ.* 124, 164–174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2016.01.022>.
- Chefaoui, R.M., Duarte, C.M., Serrão, E.A., 2018. Dramatic loss of seagrass habitat under projected climate change in the Mediterranean Sea. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 24 (10), 4919–4928. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14401>.
- CIESIN, 2024. SEDAC: Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center. <https://sedac.ciesin.columbia.edu/> [Accessed 7 Oct. 2024].
- Costanza, R., et al., 1997. The value of the world's ecosystem services and natural capital. *Nature* 387 (6630), 253–260. <https://doi.org/10.1038/387253a0>.
- Costanza, R., et al., 2014. Changes in the global value of ecosystem services. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 26, 152–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2014.04.002>.
- Cullen-Unsworth, L., Unsworth, R., 2013. Seagrass meadows, ecosystem services, and sustainability. *Environ. Sci. Policy Sustain. Dev.* 55 (3), 14–28. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00139157.2013.785864>.
- De Salvo, M., Signorello, G., 2015. Non-market valuation of recreational services in Italy: a meta-analysis. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 16, 47–62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2015.10.002>.
- Dewsbury, B.M., Bhat, M., Fourqurean, J.W., 2016. A review of seagrass economic valuations: gaps and progress in valuation approaches. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 18, 68–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2016.02.010>.
- DFS Montenegro Engineering, 2012. Start Up of "Katič" MPA in Montenegro and Assessment of Marine and Coastal Ecosystems Along the Coast.
- Duman, M., et al., 2019. Mapping *Posidonia oceanica* (Linnaeus) meadows in the eastern Aegean sea coastal areas of Turkey: evaluation of habitat maps produced using the acoustic ground discrimination systems. *International Journal of Environment and Geoinformatics* 6 (1), 67–75. <https://doi.org/10.30897/ijegeo.544695>.
- El Zrelli, R., et al., 2023. Economic losses related to the reduction of *Posidonia* ecosystem services in the Gulf of Gabes (Southern Mediterranean Sea). *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 186, 114418. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2022.114418>.
- EMODnet, 2024. EMODnet Geoviewer. <https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/geoviewer/> [Accessed 7 Oct. 2024].
- Foo, Y.Z., et al., 2021. A practical guide to question formation, systematic searching and study screening for literature reviews in ecology and evolution. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 12 (9), 1705–1720. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13654>.
- Giakoumi, S., et al., 2015. Using threat maps for cost-effective prioritization of actions to conserve coastal habitats. *Mar. Policy* 61, 95–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2015.07.004>.
- Gómez-Baggethun, E., et al., 2010. The history of ecosystem services in economic theory and practice: from early notions to markets and payment schemes. *Ecol. Econ.* 69 (6), 1209–1218. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2009.11.007>.
- Grammatikopoulou, I., Vačkářová, D., 2021. The value of forest ecosystem services: a meta-analysis at the European scale and application to national ecosystem accounting. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 48, 101262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2021.101262>.
- Griffiths, L.L., Connolly, R.M., Brown, C.J., 2020. Critical gaps in seagrass protection reveal the need to address multiple pressures and cumulative impacts. *Ocean Coast. Manag.* 183, 104946. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2019.104946>.
- de Groot, R., et al., 2012. Global estimates of the value of ecosystems and their services in monetary units. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 1 (1), 50–61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2012.07.005>.
- Pascual, U., et al., 2011. *The Economics of Valuing Ecosystem Services and Biodiversity. In: The Economics of Ecosystems and Biodiversity: Ecological and Economic Foundations.* Routledge.

- Hynes, S., et al., 2018. Marine recreational ecosystem service value estimation: a meta-analysis with cultural considerations. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 31, 410–419. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2018.02.001>.
- Johnston, R.J., Rolfe, J., Rosenberger, R.S., Brouwer, R., 2015. Benefit transfer of environmental and resource values. In: *The Economics of Non-Market Goods and Resources*, p. 14.
- Johnston, R.J., Rosenberger, R.S., 2010. Methods, trends and controversies in contemporary benefit transfer. *J. Econ. Surv.* 24 (3), 479–510. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6419.2009.00592.x>.
- Kang, N., et al., 2022. Ecosystem services valuation in China: a meta-analysis. *Sci. Total Environ.* 809, 151122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.151122>.
- Katsanevakis, S., et al., 2014. Impacts of invasive alien marine species on ecosystem services and biodiversity: a pan-European review. *Aquat. Invasions* 9 (4). <https://doi.org/10.3391/ai.2014.9.4.01>.
- Katsanevakis, S., et al., 2015. Marine conservation challenges in an era of economic crisis and geopolitical instability: the case of the Mediterranean Sea. *Mar. Policy* 51, 31–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2014.07.013>.
- Kaul, S., et al., 2013. What can we learn from benefit transfer errors? Evidence from 20 years of research on convergent validity. *J. Environ. Econ. Manag.* 66 (1), 90–104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2013.03.001>.
- Kenter, J.O., et al., 2011. The importance of deliberation in valuing ecosystem services in developing countries—evidence from the Solomon Islands. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 21 (2), 505–521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2011.01.001>.
- Kirchhoff, S., Colby, B.G., LaFrance, J.T., 1997. Evaluating the performance of benefit transfer: an empirical inquiry. *J. Environ. Econ. Manag.* 33 (1), 75–93. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jjeem.1996.0981>.
- Kubiszewski, I., et al., 2017. The future value of ecosystem services: global scenarios and national implications. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 26, 289–301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2017.05.004>.
- Lehner, B., Grill, G., 2013. Global river hydrography and network routing: baseline data and new approaches to study the world's large river systems. *Hydrol. Process.* 27 (15), 2171–2186. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.9740>.
- Liquete, C., et al., 2013. Current status and future prospects for the assessment of marine and coastal ecosystem services: a systematic review. *PLoS One* 8 (7), e67737. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0067737>.
- Liu, H., et al., 2022. A meta-regression analysis of the economic value of grassland ecosystem services in China. *Ecol. Ind.* 138, 108793. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2022.108793>.
- Lopez-Rivas, J.D., Cardenas, J.-C., 2024. What is the economic value of coastal and marine ecosystem services? A systematic literature review. *Marine Policy* 161, 106033. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2024.106033>.
- Brander, M.L., et al., 2012. Ecosystem service values for mangroves in Southeast Asia: a meta-analysis and value transfer application. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 1 (1), 62–69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2012.06.003>.
- Maes, J., et al., 2016. An indicator framework for assessing ecosystem services in support of the EU Biodiversity Strategy to 2020. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 17, 14–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2015.10.023>.
- Maouel, D., Maynou, F., Bedrani, S., 2014. Bioeconomic analysis of small pelagic fishery in Central Algeria. *Turk. J. Fish. Aquat. Sci.* 14 (4), 897–904.
- Mazor, T., Possingham, H.P., Kark, S., 2013. Collaboration among countries in marine conservation can achieve substantial efficiencies. *Divers. Distrib.* 19 (11), 1380–1393. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ddi.12095>.
- Micheli, F., et al., 2013. Cumulative human impacts on mediterranean and black sea marine ecosystems: assessing current pressures and opportunities. *PLoS One* 8 (12), e79889. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0079889>.
- Montefalcone, M., et al., 2019. Geospatial modelling and map analysis allowed measuring regression of the upper limit of *Posidonia oceanica* seagrass meadows under human pressure. *Estuar. Coast. Shelf Sci.* 217, 148–157. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2018.11.006>.
- Mtwana Nordlund, L., et al., 2016. Seagrass ecosystem services and their variability across genera and geographical regions. *PLoS One* 11 (10), e0163091.
- Navrud, S., Ready, R.C., 2007. *Environmental value transfer: issues and methods*. Springer, Dordrecht.
- Nelson, J.P., Kennedy, P.E., 2009. The use (and abuse) of meta-analysis in environmental and natural resource economics: an assessment. *Environ. Resour. Econ.* 42 (3), 345–377. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-008-9253-5>.
- Orth, R.J., et al., 2006. A global crisis for seagrass ecosystems. *Bioscience* 56 (12), 987–996. [https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568\(2006\)56\[987:AGCFSE\]2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1641/0006-3568(2006)56[987:AGCFSE]2.0.CO;2).
- Pergent-Martini, C., et al., 2021. Contribution of *Posidonia oceanica* meadows in the context of climate change mitigation in the Mediterranean Sea. *Mar. Environ. Res.* 165, 105236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marenvres.2020.105236>.
- Petersen, J.-E., et al., 2018. 'Natural capital accounting in support of policymaking in Europe: a review based on EEA ecosystem accounting work'.
- Quintas-Soriano, C., et al., 2016. Ecosystem services values in Spain: a meta-analysis. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 55, 186–195. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.10.001>.
- Rao, N.S., et al., 2015. Global values of coastal ecosystem services: a spatial economic analysis of shoreline protection values. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 11, 95–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2014.11.011>.
- Salomidi, M., et al., 2012. 'Assessment of goods and services, vulnerability, and conservation status of European seabed biotopes: a stepping stone towards ecosystem-based marine spatial management'. <https://doi.org/10.12681/mms.23>.
- de los Santos, C.B., et al., 2019. Recent trend reversal for declining European seagrass meadows. *Nat. Commun.* 10 (1), 3356. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-11340-4>.
- de los Santos, C.B., et al., 2020. 'Seagrass ecosystem services: assessment and scale of benefits', Out of the blue: The value of seagrasses to the environment and to people, pp. 19–21.
- Short, F., et al., 2007. Global seagrass distribution and diversity: a bioregional model. *J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol.* 350 (1), 3–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2007.06.012>.
- Sini, M., et al., 2017. Assembling ecological pieces to reconstruct the conservation puzzle of the Aegean Sea. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2017.00347>.
- Stamatiadou, V., et al., 2023. Valuation and mapping of the recreational diving ecosystem service of the Aegean Sea. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 64, 101569. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2023.101569>.
- Stanley, T.D., Jarrell, S.B., 2005. Meta-regression analysis: a quantitative method of literature surveys. *J. Econ. Surv.* 19 (3), 299–308. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0950-0804.2005.00249.x>.
- Tammi, I., Mustajärvi, K., Rasinmäki, J., 2017. Integrating spatial valuation of ecosystem services into regional planning and development. *Ecosyst. Serv.* 26, 329–344. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2016.11.008>.
- Taye, F.A., et al., 2021. The economic values of global forest ecosystem services: a meta-analysis. *Ecol. Econ.* 189, 107145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2021.107145>.
- Traganos, D., et al., 2022. Spatially explicit seagrass extent mapping across the entire mediterranean. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2022.871799>.
- UNEP-WCMC, S.F., 2021. 'Global distribution of seagrasses (version 7.1)', Seventh update to the data layer used in Green and Short (2003). Cambridge (UK): UN Environment World Conservation Monitoring Centre. Data DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34892/x6r3-d211> [Preprint].
- Unsworth, R.K., et al., 2010. Economic and subsistence values of the standing stocks of seagrass fisheries: potential benefits of no-fishing marine protected area management. *Ocean Coast. Manag.* 53 (5), 218.
- Unsworth, R.K.F., Nordlund, L.M., Cullen-Unsworth, L.C., 2019. Seagrass meadows support global fisheries production. *Conserv. Lett.* 12 (1), e12566. <https://doi.org/10.1111/conl.12566>.
- Van der Ploeg, S., De Groot, R.S., Wang, Y., 2010. 'The TEEB Valuation Database: overview of structure, data and results', Foundation for sustainable development, Wageningen, the Netherlands, pp. 1–247.
- Vance, C., et al., 2022. Modeling the effects of ecosystem changes on seagrass wrack valorization: merging system dynamics with life cycle assessment. *J. Clean. Prod.* 370, 133454. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.133454>.
- Vassallo, P., et al., 2013. The value of the seagrass *Posidonia oceanica*: a natural capital assessment. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 75 (1), 157–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2013.07.044>.
- Waycott, M., et al., 2009. Accelerating loss of seagrasses across the globe threatens coastal ecosystems. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 106 (30), 12377–12381. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0905620106>.
- Wohlin, C., 2014. Guidelines for snowballing in systematic literature studies and a replication in software engineering. In: *In Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering*, pp. 1–10.
- World Bank, 2024. World Development Indicators. Available at: <https://data.worldbank.org/> [Accessed 7 Oct. 2024].
- Zhou, J., Wu, J., Gong, Y., 2020. Valuing wetland ecosystem services based on benefit transfer: a meta-analysis of China wetland studies. *J. Clean. Prod.* 276, 122988. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.122988>.